

THREE-DIMENSIONAL GRAPHENE/POLYMER COMPOSITES WITH EXCEPTIONAL MULTI-FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

3D graphene materials with interconnected networks are prepared using different techniques, including template-based chemical vapor deposition to produce graphene foams (GF) and freeze-drying of graphene hydrogel to produce graphene aerogels (GA). Apart from the intrinsic properties of 2D graphene sheets, these 3D graphene materials possess other unique properties, including extremely low densities, superior electrical conductivities, and excellent elasticity and flexibility. 3D graphene/epoxy composites are prepared by infiltrating epoxy into the porous structure. GF/epoxy composites possess a cellular structure and 3D interconnected graphene network, while GA/epoxy composites possess unusual anisotropic properties due to the layered structure of GA. These composites deliver remarkable electrical conductivities, mechanical properties, and fracture toughness. These observations signify the unrivalled effectiveness of 3D graphene relative to 1D carbon nanotubes or 2D functionalized graphene sheets as reinforcement for polymer composites without the issues of nanofiller dispersion and functionalization prior to incorporation into the polymer.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene, with its exceptional mechanical and physical properties, is a prime nanofiller to be employed in nanocomposites for many multi-functional applications [1,2]. Many efforts have been made to utilize the potentials of graphene as a superior functional filler, such as alignment of graphene in polymer [3], uniform dispersion [4], and functionalization [5]. Although significant improvements have been achieved, the properties of the composites are still far from those anticipated from the inherent properties of graphene.

More recently, graphene has been assembled into three-dimensional (3D) architectures including graphene foam (GF) and graphene aerogel (GA). These 3D graphene materials have gained much interest for application in various areas, especially as electrodes in electrochemical energy devices, like rechargeable batteries, supercapacitors, and fuel cells [6,7]. GF is normally prepared through template-based chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method where atomic carbon is deposited on a porous Ni template (G-Ni) and the porous structure is preserved in GF after etching the Ni template. GA is synthesized on the use of sol-gel process where interconnected graphene hydrogel (GH) is formed via gelation of graphene oxide (GO) dispersion. Then highly porous GA is obtained through subsequent supercritical fluid drying or freeze-drying to eliminate the solvent while maintaining the intact 3D network. Apart from the intrinsic properties of 2D graphene sheets, GF and GA also possess useful attributes that other forms of 2D graphene structures lack, such as extremely large surface areas, ultralow densities, and excellent electrical and mechanical properties, making them ideal fillers for polymer composites.

A typical method to prepare 3D graphene/polymer composites is by infiltrating freestanding 3D graphene with liquid polymers. Use of the 3D interconnected GF or GA, instead of individual 2D graphene sheets, as the reinforcement of composites avoids the complicated functionalization and dispersion of individual 2D graphene sheets before adding into the polymer matrix, ultimately eliminating the problems associated with graphene agglomeration in polymers. Therefore, 3D graphene/polymer composites exhibit superior mechanical and functional properties, as compared to

those made from dispersed 2D graphene sheets [8–11]. However, the practical application of 3D/polymer composites is still at its infant stage, and very few studies have appeared in the open literature reporting their properties.

This paper reports the synthesis of GF/epoxy and GA/epoxy composites by impregnation of epoxy resin into the porous GF and GA. Their electrical and mechanical properties, fracture toughness, and toughening mechanisms were specifically evaluated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Synthesis of GF/epoxy and GA/epoxy composites

GF was synthesized by a CVD method while GA was prepared by one-step chemical reduction and rational self-assembly of GO sheets using hydroiodic (HI) acid followed by freeze-drying, as described in our recent studies [12,13]. The SEM images of GF and GA are shown in Figure 1. GF/epoxy composites were fabricated by infiltration of liquid epoxy into the porous GF. The epoxy resin (LY1556, Huntsman Advanced Materials), the curing agent (triethylenetetramine), and acetone were mixed in a weight ratio of 20:12:100. The G-Ni foam was immersed into the epoxy resin system for 0.5 h to form a prepreg followed by degassing in a vacuum oven at room temperature (RT) for 5 h. A desired number of prepreg layers were stacked in an aluminium mold and hot-pressed at 80 °C for 0.5 h at a pressure of 0.5 MPa, followed by further curing at 110 °C for 1.5 h. The Ni template was removed by immersing the cured composites into a concentrated HCl (3M) at 80 °C for 48 h. After rinsing with DI water, the composites were further treated at 120 °C for 2 h to eliminate any stresses arising from the chemical etching and were slowly cooled to RT in the furnace. GA/epoxy composites were fabricated using a vacuum-assisted infiltration method where GA was immersed into the epoxy resin system prepared without acetone, which was degassed in vacuum at 60 °C for 1h. The liquid composite was cured at 80 °C for 30 min and post-cured at 110 °C for 2 h to produce a solid composite plate of thickness ~6.0 mm. The graphene content of GA/epoxy composites was controlled by changing the concentration of initial GO dispersion.

Figure 1: SEM images of (a) GF and (b) GA.

2.2 Characterization

The morphologies of GAs and GFs, the fracture surfaces of their composites were examined on scanning electron microscopes (SEM, JEOL 6390F and JEOL JSM-6700F). The electrical conductivities of the composites were measured based on the four-point probe method (Scientific Equipment & Services). The flexural and fracture toughness tests were performed on a universal testing machine at RT according to the specifications, ASTM D790 and ASTM D5045, respectively [12,13].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Electrical properties

Graphene has been extensively studied to make highly conductive polymer composites due to its high aspect ratio and exceptional electron mobility. However, the electrical conductivities of graphene/polymer nanocomposites prepared by direct dispersion of few-layer graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) or rGO sheets into the polymer are not very impressive. In view of this, constructing a 3D interconnected network as the fast transport channel of charge carriers in the insulating polymer matrix is an efficient way of realizing rapid insulator-to-conductor transition and achieving excellent electrical conductivities [14].

Figure 2a shows the electrical conductivities of GF/epoxy composites. With the addition of 0.1 wt% GF, they exhibited a remarkable 12 orders of magnitude increase in electrical conductivity, with a percolation occurring approximately at 0.05 wt%. With no residual Ni template in the composites [12], the above exceptional electrical conducting performance can be ascribed to the high electron mobility offered by the seamlessly interconnected 3D network of high-quality GF. Besides, the CVD grown GF does not require usual reduction processes to restore the inherent conductivity of graphene. The inset in Figure 2a shows a maximum conductivity of 6.4 S/cm with four layers of graphene, or 0.16 wt% GF in the composite. A further increase in GF content beyond 0.38 wt%, or about seven graphene layers, resulted in a rather saturated conductivity. Interestingly, the conductivity of freestanding GF was consistently higher than the composites until they gradually converged at higher GF contents. One possible reason is that the conducting structure of the GF at low contents is partially damaged during the epoxy infiltration process.

Similar to the GF/epoxy composites, the GA/epoxy composites also possess remarkable electrical properties as shown in Figure 2b, benefiting from 3D interconnected graphene structure of GA. The electrical conductivity surged from 10^{-12} S/cm for the neat epoxy to 2×10^{-3} S/cm for the composites by 9 orders when only 0.25 wt% graphene was added. It's interesting to note that the conductivities were basically identical in the orthogonal directions for graphene contents less than ~0.5 wt%. Above that, the conductivity was gradually higher in the alignment direction than in the transverse direction, and the largest discrepancy of 0.08 S/cm is attained at graphene content of 1.4 wt%, which is equivalent to 67% of the conductivity measured in the transverse direction (see inset in Figure 2b). The anisotropic electrical conductivities at high graphene contents are the consequence of the alignment of graphene from 0.5-0.7 wt%, below which the structure of GA was random and macroscopically isotropic. As highlighted in Figure 2b, the much lower conductivity in the transverse direction is possibly resulted from some disconnected paths, especially at the junctions where the horizontal layers meet the transverse supporting sheets.

A comparison of electrical conductivities between the current study and the literature with epoxy-based nanocomposites containing 2D graphene and 1D CNTs, is shown in Figure 2c. It's clearly seen that both GF/epoxy and GA/epoxy composites exhibit superior conductivities, especially GF/epoxy composites, which is at least 3 orders of magnitude higher than those of containing GNP, rGO and CNTs [3,14,15]. The excellent electrical conductivities of GF/epoxy and GA/epoxy composites are testament to a higher efficiency of the 3D interconnected graphene structure in forming conductive networks than any other forms of carbon materials.

Figure 2: (a) Electrical conductivities of GF/epoxy composites as a function of GF content. The conductivity of freestanding GF is superimposed in inset of (a); (b) electrical conductivities of GA/epoxy composites in orthogonal directions; and (c) comparison of electrical conductivities of epoxy-based nanocomposites containing graphene and CNTs.

3.2 Flexural properties and fracture toughness

The flexural properties of both composites are plotted as a function of graphene content in Figure 3. The incorporation of GF into the epoxy significantly increased both the flexural modulus and strength compared to the solid neat epoxy, as shown in Figure 3a. The maximum values were obtained at ~0.2 wt% GF with 53% and 38% improvements, respectively, followed by moderate reductions with further increase in GF content. However, the corresponding flexural properties of GA/epoxy composites showed relatively limited increases due to the moderate interfacial adhesion between the untreated rGO and the epoxy matrix [13]. It is of interest to note that both the properties measured in the transverse direction showed a peak at 0.5 wt% graphene, followed by gradual reductions with higher graphene contents. The transition in these properties means that the reinforcement effect started to decrease in the transverse direction above 0.5 wt% graphene content. A similar transition was also observed for the electrical conductivity (Figure 2b).

Figure 3: Flexural strength and modulus of (a) GF/epoxy composites; and (b,c) GA/epoxy composites.

The fracture toughness K_{IC} of the composites was measured, as shown in Figures 4a and b. The K_{IC} value of GF/epoxy composites increased sharply to $1.78 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ with 0.1 wt% GF, corresponding to a remarkable enhancement of 70% compared to the solid epoxy. A further rise in GF content resulted in saturation or marginal reductions (Figure 4a) probably because the increased graphene layers only led to slippage between the adjacent layers to disrupt the weak van der Waals forces when the composites were stressed by an external load [4]. Unlike the modulus and strength, the GA/epoxy composites presented much improved toughness in the alignment direction (with a crack propagating perpendicular to the alignment). The K_{IC} value surged to $1.46 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ with only 0.25 wt% graphene, equivalent to an enhancement of over 47% compared to the neat epoxy. A further increase in graphene content resulted in only a moderate increase in K_{IC} , with a total of 64% enhancement for 1.4 wt% graphene. However, the K_{IC} value of the same composites in the transverse direction presented an entirely different behaviour. It initially increased similar to that measured in the alignment direction for graphene contents up to 0.5 wt%, followed by large drops with further increase in graphene content, thus resulting in 23% lower fracture toughness than the neat epoxy at 1.4 wt% graphene. This finding is similar to the flexural properties (Figure 3), with the transition of the properties between the two directions occurring consistently at about 0.5 wt% graphene.

To signify the advantages of 3D graphene reinforcement, fracture toughness K_{IC} values of epoxy-based nanocomposites containing graphene sheets and CNTs from the literature are compared with the current study in Figure 4c. For CNT/epoxy composites, the increase in K_{IC} was typically low, presenting 25% improvement with 0.5 wt% CNTs [16]. Graphene-based composites showed generally better performance: GNP and rGO/epoxy composites had 40 to 53 % enhancements, respectively [15,17]. The performance of 3D graphene composites were among the best for all graphene contents. This comparison reveals much more effective reinforcement of 3D interconnected GF in enhancing fracture resistance toughness of nanocomposites than 1D CNTs, 2D GNP or rGO sheets.

Figure 4: Mode I fracture toughness, K_{IC} , of (a) GF/epoxy composites; (b) GA/epoxy composites; and (c) comparison of fracture toughness between epoxy-based nanocomposites containing graphene and CNTs.

3.3 Toughening mechanisms

The SEM images of the fracture surfaces of the neat epoxy, GF/epoxy and GA/epoxy composites are shown in Figure 5 to study the toughening mechanisms. The fracture surface of the neat epoxy displayed a smooth and featureless surface, which is typical of brittle fracture of homogeneous thermoset polymers, indicating very weak resistance to crack propagation. The fracture surface of GF/epoxy composites, however, presents coarse, multi-plane features with numerous protuberances of their sizes equivalent to the spherical cells between the GF networks (Figure 5b). However, no clear evidence of crack pinning – one of the most important failure mechanisms in rigid particulate-reinforced composites – was identified. Instead, the crack tips were blunted by the seamlessly interconnected GF walls before collapse to induce winding crack tip deflections. As a result, the cracks tended to tilt, twist or bifurcate along the boundary of GF under mixed modes of tension and shear to leave mound-shaped crack paths through the epoxy matrix. Thus, the crack propagation under the mixed-mode condition resulted in the formation of protuberances with a much increased fracture surface area after the collapse of GF reinforcements [12], requiring a higher energy absorption than in pure mode I tension.

For GA/epoxy composites, crack deflection also played an important role in enhancing the fracture toughness. Unlike the composites reinforced with isolated carbon nanotubes or graphene sheets, cracks in GA composites were not able to bypass or bow out through the interconnected GA. This means when the crack grew transverse to the alignment, they always had to break the interconnected graphene, causing significant crack tip deflection and dissipating a large amount of fracture energy. This assumption is partly verified by the “stair-like” fracture surface in the composite with 1.4 wt% graphene (Figure 5c), a reflection of crack tip deflection due to the presence of interconnected rGO sheets that are aligned at different planes. The tendency of crack deflection increased with increasing graphene content, leaving behind a high surface roughness [13]. In contrast, however, when the cracks

propagated along the alignment direction, a flat and featureless fracture surface was obtained (Figure 5d) as a result of easy crack growth along the moderately-bonded interface between the rGO and epoxy or through the weakly bonded rGO layers. This finding is further proven by the large rGO sheets exposed on the fracture surface, as highlighted in Figure 5d.

Figure 5: SEM images of quasi-static fracture surfaces of (a) neat epoxy; (b) GF/epoxy composites with 0.1 wt% GF; and GA/epoxy composites with 1.4 wt% graphene: cracks propagating (c) against the alignment direction and (d) along the alignment direction. Blue arrow indicates the direction of crack propagation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper reports the synthesis of 3D graphene materials with interconnected networks using two techniques, such as template-based CVD to produce GF; and freeze-drying of GH to produce GA. 3D graphene/epoxy composites were prepared by infiltrating a liquid polymer into their porous structures. The GF/epoxy composites possessed a remarkable electrical conductivity of 3 S/cm at 0.2 wt% GF and a low percolation threshold of 0.05 wt% thanks to the 3D integrated cellular structure. There was a notable 53% and 38% enhancements in flexural modulus and strength at ~0.2 wt% GF, respectively. A remarkable 70% enhancement in fracture toughness of the composites compared to the solid epoxy was obtained at 0.1 wt% GF. Crack tip blunting and deflection due to the porous GF network were the major toughening mechanisms responsible for the enhanced fracture toughness. They functioned as crack arresters leading to crack propagation under a mixed-mode condition, creating a rough fracture surface and a larger surface area.

GA/epoxy composites had 3D framework with interconnected rGO layers that are aligned in one direction at graphene contents above 0.5 wt%. The preferential alignment of rGO sheets resulted in anisotropic mechanical properties and electrical conductivity. The electrical conductivity of the composite was 0.2 S/m with 0.25 wt% graphene, much higher than those of the composites made from

rGO sheets. A remarkable 64% enhancement in fracture toughness compared to the neat epoxy was achieved at 1.4 wt% graphene content in the direction perpendicular to the alignment. Breakage of 3D interconnected GA structure and crack deflection explained the enhanced fracture toughness, showing larger fracture surface roughness with increasing graphene content. Due to the anisotropic structure of GA, the properties measured in the alignment direction were much higher than the transverse direction above 0.5 wt%.

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